

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Habayeb**FIRST NAME:** Mayy**PROGRAM CODE:** DIDOL**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 06**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (Word for Mac version 16.94)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, what is academic essay writing about?

Academic essay writing is non-fictional writing produced as part of scholarly work. It is based on research findings or empirical field work, which may or may not be published in journals or other media.¹

Academic essay writing is a form of fictional writing produced as part of scholarly work.

Academic essay writing is non-fictional writing produced as part of scholarly work based on the researcher's imagination.

¹Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

- Academic essay writing is non-fictional writing produced as part of scholarly work based on the researcher's subjective interpretation of a short story, where the researcher creates novel narratives.

2. **In which of the following cases don't you need to cite a reference for a fact?**

- When using data collected by another researcher, but the researcher hasn't published it yet.
- When it is common knowledge and can be found in many sources.²**
- When you reuse a diagram from another journal article that has already been published.
- When you rewrite an idea expressed in a book using your own words.

3. **Kate Turabian explains three key elements researchers need to identify to formulate their research aim: Topic, research question(s), and ...?**

- Hypotheses related to the research questions.
- Significance of the research.³**
- Citation of the sources.
- Methods used in the research.

² Ibid., 37.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 200.

4. **According to Kate Turabian, a research argument is assembled in the form of answers to five elements. Which of the following are the five elements?**
- Claim, hypotheses, significance, evidence, and warrants.
 - Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgement, response, and warrants.**⁴
 - Claim, research question, evidence, significance, and warrants.
 - Claim, reason, evidence, methods, and warrants.
5. **According to Kate Turabian, researchers have two primary duties once they formulate an argument. Which of the following best expresses these two primary duties?**
- The first is to collect data, and the second is to analyze the data.
 - The first is to write a draft, and the second is to cite the sources.
 - The first is to get the correct facts to support the research problem, and the second is to tell the readers where the facts came from by properly citing the sources they came from.**⁵
 - The first is to identify a research problem, and the second is to create an argument.
6. **Writing style, such as capitalization, names, and grammar, is essential for professional academic writing. Which of the following is correct according to the Turabian guide guidelines?**

⁴ Ibid., 58.

⁵ Ibid., 139.

- The festival of light is scheduled in Spring, which happens to be the first Tuesday in March.
- The festival of light is scheduled in spring, which happens to be the first Tuesday in march.
- The festival of light is scheduled in spring, which happens to be the first Tuesday in March.⁶**
- The festival of light is scheduled in spring, which happens to be the first tuesday in March.

7. **According to Linda Bloomberg and Marie VOLPE, the second chapter in a qualitative research dissertation is the literature review. Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of this chapter?**

- This chapter aims to systematically identify, locate, and analyze the material related to the research problem to educate and gain the reader's confidence in the research work.⁷**
- This chapter describes the rationale of the research approach, the sample and population data, and how the study is designed.
- This chapter aims to clarify the research findings for the reader.
- This chapter aims to clarify what should be studied and why it is worth exploring.

⁶ Ibid., 330.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, 4th edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 345–428.

8. According to James Sampson, research questions, hypotheses, the research design, and the measures all identify the variables included in the dissertation research. How are variables measured in qualitative research?

- An instrument with several scales can measure variables in qualitative research, with one variable operationalized by one scale.
- Variables in qualitative research can be measured by focus group questions, with one variable operationalized by one focus group.⁸**
- Variables in qualitative research can be measured by response to an advertisement scale. With one variable operationalized by one advertisement.
- Variables in qualitative research can be measured by chart analysis with several scales. With one variable operationalized per chart.

9. Complete the following sentence from the Turabian guide about the order of the structure of your dissertation: The best order is the one _____.

- that best meets your publisher's needs.
- that best meets the complexity of the analysis you conducted.
- that best meets your readers' needs.⁹**
- that best meets your advisor's needs.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research, Second Edition*, second. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 36.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition*, 72.

10. Why do you think Kate Turabian advises researchers to write the title of the academic work last?

- The title is the first thing readers read and should convey the topic and the problem statement.
- The title is the first thing readers read and should convey the topic and the working hypotheses.
- The title is the first thing readers read and should convey the topic and the methodology.
- The title is the first thing readers read and should convey the topic and the conceptual framework.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Ibid., 115.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research, Second Edition*. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.